

ENERGY MODELLING PLATFORM – AFRICA | 2023

Investigation of the Financial Viability of C&I Solar Systems

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1. Context

- Zambia has a total Installed Generation Capacity of 3777.3 MW with 2% being solar.
- National Energy Demand (2022) is 13,777,900 MWh.
- Photovoltaic Power Potential for Lusaka is 4.3kwh per square meter.
- Population (2021) stands at 19.47 Million.
- Inflation is 8.9% (2023).
- Project Finance Interest rates from public Institutions is 12% per annum.

2. Aim

- This investigation aims to establish the financial viability using the system size for Commercial and Industrial Solar PV systems in Zambia.

3. Methods & Scenarios

- FINPLAN is utilised for the Study.
- Energy Tariffs is 1.3, Inflation is 8 %, Exchange Rate is 18.3, Project Finance Interest rate is 12% per annum.
- Systems Size, Dividends, Investment, NPV, IRR for Project Sizes 100 – 1000 KW (steps of 100) are compared.
- A sensitivity analysis is conducted for the minimum viable system size (NPV & IRR).

4. Results

- The NPV shows a high rate of increase from 100 kw to 200 kw system size.
- Increasing the energy tariff by 30% starts the payment of Dividends 5 years earlier.

PARAMETERS CHANGED	PARAMETERS STUDIED	BASE CASE	SCENARIO
Exchange Rate	1. Dividend 2. NPV and IRR 3. Revenue	Base case 18.3 ZMW	Exchange rate is increased by 31%
Energy Tariff	1. Dividend 2. NPV and IRR 3. Revenue	Base case 1.3 ZMW	Energy tariff is increased by 30%

Table 1.

Figure 1.

5. Policy insights, conclusions and future work

- Conclusions: NPV and IRR better for a 200 KW system and Higher. Tariffs and Exchange rate can largely affect NPV and IRR,
- Policy insights: Lending Interest rates can attractive investments especially from public financial Institutions. A Carbon Credit framework can reduce costs of Investment.
- Future work: A sensitivity analysis that can consider more parameters (Interest rate, discount rate etc) can provide insights into the resilience of the system to economic changes.

6. References

- [1] <https://www.erb.org.zm/>
- [2] <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications>
- [3] <https://www.irena.org/publications>